

RECOMMENDATIONS ON MISSING ASPECTS IN STANDARDISATION AND REGULATION OF BIO-BASED MATERIALS AND PRODUCTS

ViSS builds a safe and sustainable value chain for PHBV bioplastics from food industry residues to high-performance packaging. ViSS aims to demonstrate that bio-based plastics can match fossil-based alternatives in performance while ensuring safety, full recyclability, and biodegradability in all environments. By creating a circular value chain, ViSS drives the transition towards a sustainable future, where replacing fossil-based consumer plastics is essential for decarbonising society.

POLICY BRIEF

Background

The progressive substitution of fossil-based plastics is essential to support EU climate-neutrality and circular economy objectives. Bioplastics offer a promising alternative, particularly when derived from renewable natural sources and supported by sustainable production systems ^a. However, **market penetration remains low – around 1%**. Advances in biotechnology and green chemistry are improving material performance and processing efficiency, contributing to greater commercial viability ^b. But the high cost of bioplastics still represents a barrier to widespread adoption, especially in sectors where cost is a decisive factor, such as packaging and consumer goods ^c.

The use of alternative feedstocks – agricultural residues and non-food biomass, can reduce production costs and lessen environmental impacts ^d. Nevertheless, **biodegradation behaviour remains strongly dependent on environmental conditions**, as certain bioplastics do not degrade effectively in natural ecosystems (e.g. soil or marine environments), underscoring a need for clearer design criteria and end-of-life guidance ^e.

Harmonised sustainability criteria, transparent environmental claims and EU-wide standardisation frameworks are becoming increasingly critical. Evidence shows that national policies, certification schemes and bioeconomy standards play a decisive role in enabling market acceptance and sector expansion ^{f,g,h}.

Categorisation of bioplastics depending on their material origin and biodegradability.

Challenges

- 1 Science-based regulatory frameworks are needed.** Existing EN/ISO standards, built for conventional plastics, do not fully address bio-based properties, performance or end-of-life pathways.
- 2 Key terms vary across standards, creating confusion.** Limited data on bio-based materials and their environmental impacts further restricts robust assessments.
- 3 End-of-life infrastructures are not sufficiently adapted to bio-based polymers.** This can cause improper disposal for consumers and industry.
- 4 New bio-based materials often lack recyclability, compostability or reuse criteria at the design stage.** Limited data on bio-based materials and their environmental impacts restricts robust sustainability assessments.
- 5 Safe-and-Sustainable-by Design (SSbD) principles are not fully applied in the development, assessment and standardisation of bioplastics.** Inadequate value-chain traceability hampers transparency and reliable labelling.

ViSS solutions and recommendations

Map regulatory and standardisation gaps across the full life cycle

- Strengthen, harmonise and update EU definitions and metrics for bio-based materials
- Harmonise biodegradability and compostability criteria across environments, with clear performance thresholds and test methods.

Provide clear and reliable information across the value chain

- Implement robust traceability systems and standardised labelling to ensure accurate value chain information and prevent misleading claims.
- Develop a standardised and integrated SSbD framework to enable comparable, science-based assessments adapted to bio-based solutions.

Foster waste management end-of-life strategies for the biobased materials

- Upgrade sorting and recycling systems to ensure that bio-based plastic materials are properly identified and processed.
- Expand and improve composting infrastructure to handle certified compostable bio-based plastics.

Align the life cycle of bio-based plastics with circular economy principles

- Promote alternative feedstocks to reduce reliance on food crops, lower costs and enhance sustainable sourcing.
- Integrate end-of-life performance criteria into polymer design to ensure compatibility with recycling, composting or biodegradation.

Create supportive framework conditions for the growth of bio-based value chains

- Establish supportive policy and financial frameworks (e.g., incentives, tax credits, R&D funding) to accelerate bio-based value chain development.
- Advance safe and sustainable bio-based plastics with SSbD principles throughout the innovation chain by fostering cross-sector collaboration.

Conclusions

ViSS project contributes to addressing the main barriers affecting the deployment of bioplastics by developing a PHBV circular value chain aligned with EU sustainability and safety requirements. By identifying regulatory and standardisation gaps and providing evidence-based recommendations, ViSS strengthens social readiness, traceability and market acceptance of bio-based materials. These efforts support the EU's broader objective of scaling safe, sustainable and competitive bio-based solutions across European industries.

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